

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF ALLIED HEALTH SCIENCES

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF BOARD OF STUDIES HELD ON 10.06.2021 AT 9:30 AM IN THE BOARD ROOM

Members present:

1. Prof. Devaseelan S	Chairman
2. Mr. Naveen Bappanadu	Member
3. Mrs. Swathi D	Member
4. Ms. Varsha A C	Member
5. Ms. Kavya Shettigar K	Member
6. Mrs. Swathi Krishnan	Member
7. Mr. Jibin Simon	Member
8. Mrs. Priyadhersini. S	Member
9. Dr. Sohan Rodney Bangera	Member
10. Dr. Vrinda J Bhat	External Member
11. Dr. David Rosario	External Member
12. B Balaji Narayan	Industrial Expert

The BOS discussed the following agenda:

1. Approve the minutes of the last Meeting of the BOS held on 05.03.2021.
2. Online and Offline Classes were proposed
3. BOS Members were updated
4. Discussion related to Elective Subjects

Agenda No. 1: Confirmations of the minutes of Last Meeting of Board of Studies which was held on 12.06.2020. The Resolution was taken as per the suggestions of the BOS Members in the last meeting, all the Allied Health Sciences Courses were asked to update the changes proposed by the BOS Members.

Agenda No. 2: The suggestion was given by the BOS member that the Offline classes to be commenced. As there is a need for the offline classes the decision was made to

Agenda No. 3: Conducting Clinical Posting and Practical Sessions – Related: Covid-19 and Lockdown issues. The Resolution was such that as the Covid Norms the Campus had to be closed for few weeks and hence the students who were needing the Clinical Posting and Practical Sessions and were allowed to be present in the campus with Negative Covid Test report

Agenda No. 4: Discussion related to Elective Subject was made. The Chairperson suggested to start with Open Elective and Discipline Elective Subjects. Resolution was taken accordingly, and Changes were approved as proposed by the BOS.

The meeting was concluded at 11:30 AM with a vote of thanks by Ms. Swathi Krishnan, Member and Board of Studies.

Prof. Devaseelan S,
Chairman,
BOS in Allied Health Science

Members present:

Prof. Devaseelan S

Mr. Naveen Bappanadu

Mrs. Swathi D

Ms. Varsha A C

Ms. Kavya Shettigar K

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